

Adsorption of biomolecules on the surface of nanomaterials: A meta-modeling approach integrating molecular modeling with machine learning

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Abstract

The adsorption of biomolecules on the surface of nanomaterials (NMs) is a critical determinant of their behavior, toxicity, and efficacy in biological systems. Experimental testing of these phenomena is often costly or complicated. Computational approaches, particularly those integrating methods of various theoretical levels, can provide essential insights into nano-bio interactions and bio-corona formation, facilitating the efficient design of nanomaterials for biomedical applications. This study presents a meta-modeling approach that integrates physics-based molecular modeling with machine learning algorithms to predict the interaction energy between NMs and biomolecules extracted from potentials of mean force (PMF). Novel descriptors for the surface properties of NMs are developed and combined with structural descriptors of biomolecules to derive quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR). The developed QSPR model helps the understanding and predicting the interactions between NMs (including carbon-based, metals, metal oxides, metalloids, and cadmium selenide) and biomolecules thus facilitating safe and sustainable design of nanomaterials for various applications, particularly for nanomedicine. An application for surface descriptors of nanomaterials is available at GitHub.

1 Introduction

Nanomaterials (NMs) have attracted significant attention recently due to their unique properties arising from their large specific surface area, small size, high stability, reactivity, and versatility for functionalization [1]. These features have led to the widespread use of NMs in various fields, including medicine, electronics, and environmental science [2, 3]. However, the interaction of NMs with biological systems remains an area of active research, particularly regarding the formation of protein corona upon entering biological environments [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. This protein corona, resulting from the adsorption of proteins and other biomolecules onto the surface of NMs, can significantly influence toxicokinetics, and efficacy of NMs in biological applications [9, 10, 11]. Understanding the molecular interactions at the bio-nano interface is crucial for various applications, such as developing reliable medical implants, improving biosensor surfaces, and designing novel NMs with tailored properties [9, 10, 11]. However, the complexity of these interactions, coupled with the diverse physicochemical properties of both NMs and biomolecules, poses a significant challenge for researchers [12, 13].

To address this challenge, the present study aimed to investigate biomolecule adsorption on the surface of nanomaterials using a computational approach as an alternative to infeasible experimental studies. To optimize the use of computational resources, we applied meta-modeling approach integrating molecular modeling (MM) - a cost-intensive physics-based method of high theoretical level, with a machine learning (ML) approach, which is a cost-effective, data-based method enabling generalization and predictions for untested systems. We investigated interactions between nanomaterials i.e., carbonaceous materials, metals, metal oxides, metalloids, and semiconductors, with biomolecules such as amino acids. MM allowed for evaluation of reliable interaction energy profile expressed as the Potential of Mean Force (PMF), by exploring potential energy hypersurfaces through metadynamics (MTD) [14, 15, 16, 17, 18]. In turn, the AdaBoost ML algorithm allowed for the development of a quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) model to predict the adsorption energy, a key determinant in bio-corona formation [10, 19, 20, 12, 13]. This model is based on newly proposed descriptors for the surface properties of nanomaterials and established structural descriptors of biomolecules. The identified key descriptors influencing adsorption energy provide a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms of protein corona formation and its implications for nanotoxicity and nanomaterials' biocompatibility [21, 22, 23, 20]. This knowledge will enable the design of novel nanomaterials with tailored properties, optimized for specific biological interactions and applications.

The proposed meta-modeling approach, incorporating both physics-based and data-driven methods, facilitates the prediction of potential NMs' toxicokinetics and hazards at the early stage of the product design and

Figure 1: Structures of 15 biomolecules used in the study (extra validation set).

Table 1: Groups of molecular descriptors used to characterize the physicochemical properties of basic AAs, as defined by the alvaDesc software.

Name of descriptors group
Constitutional indices
Ring descriptors
Topological indices
P_VSA-like descriptors
ETA indices
Geometrical descriptors
Functional group counts
Atom-centered fragments
Atom-type E-state indices
Pharmacophore descriptors
2D Atom Pairs
3D Atom Pairs
Charge descriptors
Molecular properties
MDE (molecular distance edge)

More information about descriptor groups:
<https://www.alvascience.com/alvadesc-descriptors/>.

thus aligns with the overarching paradigm of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) of novel NMs [24, 25, 26].
 The development of such a model is crucial for advancing the field of NM research and ensuring the safe and
 sustainable use of NMs in various applications [27, 28, 29, 30, 31].

2 Methods

2.1 Biomolecules & structural descriptors

In this study, we used 15 natural amino acids (AAs), i.e., ALA, ARG, ASN, ASP, CYS, GLN, GLU, ILE, LEU, LYS, PHE, PRO, SER, TRP, TYR (forming training and validation set) and 15 other biomolecules (shown in Figure 1) To characterize their structural features, we utilized molecular descriptors generated by the alvaDesc software [32]. Our selection encompassed 116 descriptors chosen from a pool categorized into 15 groups (Table 1). The calculated descriptors are available in supplementary materials (SupplementMaterialData.xlsx, sheets: AADescriptors, ExtraMoleculesDescriptors). This comprehensive approach aimed to ensure a thorough representation of the biomolecules' diverse physicochemical attributes.

2.2 Nanomaterials - quantum-mechanical & surface descriptors

In this study we investigated nano-bio interactions of 20 NMs, including i) carbon-based i.e., amorphous carbon, modified carbon nanotubes and graphene; ii) metals i.e., silver and gold; iii) metal oxides i.e., titanium dioxide, iron (III) oxide; iv) metalloid oxide, i.e., silicon dioxide; v) cadmium selenide. To perform quantum-mechanical (QM) calculations for NMs' descriptors, we redefined the structure of each NM by selecting representative molecular fragments from the non-relaxed portions of the NM structures (i.e., without geometry optimization), thereby preserving the original crystal structures. These fragments were chosen to be large enough to retain the key NM properties, yet small enough to allow for feasible QM calculations (Figure 2, Step 1) The size of each NM cluster was determined by the size of the largest AAs (in our case: arginine) to enable the proper

Table 2: Descriptors for NMs used in this study, divided into three categories: surface properties, electronic properties (calculated in the presence of a finite dipole), and other properties.

1. NMs' descriptors calculated per unit surface area [\AA^2]	
Number of rotatable bonds	Number of single bonds (i.e., not involved in a ring structure) on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Molecular roughness	Number of functional groups sticking out of the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Number of atoms	Number of atoms on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Number of electron-lone-pair-donor atoms	Number of atoms capable of donating their electron lone pair on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Number of sp^2 carbon atoms	Number of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Σ Pauling electronegativity	Pauling electronegativity values summed over the atoms on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Σ qNBO	Natural Bond Orbital partial atomic charges (in a.u.) summed over the atoms on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Σ qMull	Mulliken partial atomic charges (in a.u.) summed over the atoms on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
Σ qESP	Merz-Kollman (i.e., fitted to the electrostatic potential) partial atomic charges (in a.u.) summed over the atoms on the NM's surface per \AA^2 .
2. Descriptors reflecting the electronic properties of NM's surface, calculated in the presence of a finite dipole	
FDV1 and FDV2 (finite dipole vertical)	Interaction energy (in kcal/mol) between the NM and the finite dipole (consisting of $+1e$ and $-1e$ point charges separated by 3\AA) localized perpendicularly to the NM's surface and separated from it by 5\AA . The $(-, +)$ indicates that the dipole's negative pole is closer to the NM's surface than the positive pole whereas $(+, -)$ indicates reverse orientation.
FDH1 and FDH2 (finite dipole horizontal)	Interaction energy (in kcal/mol) between the NM and the finite dipole (consisting of $+1e$ and $-1e$ point charges separated by 3\AA) localized horizontally to the NM's surface and separated from it by 5\AA . The '1' and '2' indices indicate two different orientations of the dipole (in FDH2, the dipole is rotated by 180 deg (along the axis perpendicular to the NM's surface) with respect to the FDH1).
FDV _{mean}	Averaged interaction energy with a vertically oriented dipole
FDH _{mean}	Averaged interaction energy with a horizontally oriented dipole
3. Others	
General characteristic of nanostructure:	
Non-metal mole fraction	Mole fraction of the non-metal atoms on the NM's surface.
Metal mole fraction	Mole fraction of the metal atoms on the NM's surface.
QM descriptors:	
Dipole moment	Dipole moment (in Debye) calculated for NM.
Quadrupole moment	$1/3$ of the trace of the diagonalized quadrupole moment matrix (in Debye $\times\text{\AA}$) predicted for NM.

71 interaction of the AAs with the surface of the NM. In the case of a nanotube, we used the half-cylinder shape
72 cut to preserve the curvature of the NM. The thickness of the nanoparticle's fragment was reduced (preserving
73 its crystal structure) to make QM calculations feasible. Once the representative fragments of all NMs were
74 selected, we investigated NMs properties relevant to the adsorption of biomolecules on NMs' surface using
75 reliable density functional theory (DFT) [33, 34] method (B3LYP functional) [35, 36]. We performed our
76 calculations using (i) the Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) effective core potentials (ECP) with the
77 appropriate valence basis set of double zeta quality (denoted LANL2DZ) [37, 38, 37] (for NMs containing Ag,
78 Au, Cd, and Se atoms), (ii) the 4-31G basis set (for carbon-based NMs) [39], and (iii) the 3-21G basis set (for the
79 remaining NMs) [40].” As a result, we calculated a set of QM descriptors like HOMO/LUMO energy, electronic
80 energy, partial atomic charges (according to the NBO, Mulliken, and Merz-Kollman population analysis), dipole
81 moment, and quadrupole moment; and proposed two types of novel descriptors to accurately describe NMs'
82 surface properties (Table 2, and SupplementMaterialData.xlsx, sheet: NanoDescriptors). The calculated NMs'
83 descriptors can be divided into three main categories:

- 84 1. Descriptors characterizing the surface of NMs, calculated per unit surface area (given as values per \AA^2).
- 85 2. Descriptors reflecting the electronic properties of NMs surface, calculated in the presence of a finite dipole.
- 86 3. Others: general characteristics of NMs from QM calculations.

87 As shown in Figure 2 (path A), the descriptors belonging to category 1 required defining a quasi-flat fragment
88 of a surface as the adsorption of small biomolecules is assumed to take place only on such a fragment. The
89 selection of such a flat fragment was relatively easy when considering cubic crystal structures of NMs e.g., TiO_2
90 or CdSe , for which one face of the cube could be selected as a flat fragment. However, making the analogous
91 selection in the case of NMs having either spherical or cylindrical shape was more complicated. First, we had
92 to recognize the largest nearly flat fragment of the NM's surface and calculate its area (by multiplying vectors
93 $\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = (a_2 - a_1) \times (b_2 - b_1)$). Next, we computed the descriptors belonging to the 1 category by considering
94 only the atoms contained in the chosen nearly flat fragment (see Table 2).

95 The determination of the 2 category descriptors reflecting the electronic properties of the NM surface was
96 performed in the presence of a finite dipole composed of a pair of point charges, $+1|e|$ and $-1|e|$, separated
97 by 3\AA (see Figure 2, path B). These calculations required extra files containing information on the dipole

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the procedure for calculating descriptors for NMs. Step 1 involves selecting a representative fragment of the NM structure. Path A shows the calculation of surface descriptors based on the size of the surface area. Path B illustrates the calculation of electronic properties in the presence of a finite dipole.

orientation with respect to the NM. In particular, these files included the location of the center of the dipole (above the center of the selected NM's face, 5 Å away from the surface of the NM, at the point $(a/2; b/2)$, where a and b are the edges of the selected fragment of the NM. The 5 Å separation between the dipole and the NM was set as the distance between the outermost atom on the NM's surface and either the center of the dipole (for FDH descriptors) or the closest dipole's point charge (for FDV descriptors). Hence, for each NM we considered four different dipole orientations:

- FDH1 - (+/-) dipole oriented horizontally relative to the NM's surface,
- FDH2 - (-/+) dipole oriented horizontally relative to the NM's surface,
- FDV1 - (+/-) dipole oriented vertically relative to the NM's surface, with its positive pole closer to NM,
- FDV2 - (-/+) dipole oriented vertically relative to the NM's surface, with its negative pole closer to NM.

In order to obtain the averaged dipole-NM interaction energies, the DFT calculations were performed for all four orientations of the dipole with respect to the NM surface. The dipole-NM interaction energies were then acquired by subtracting the energy of a given NM (obtained in the absence of a dipole) from that of the NM with the dipole present. Since the dipole-NM interaction energies were always negative (as the presence of a dipole stabilizes the system and thus decreases its total energy), the final values of the FDH and FDV descriptors were taken as the absolute values of the averaged dipole-NM interaction energies i.e., the values of (+/-) and (-/+) for FDH and FDV, respectively. During the pre-selection process (Descriptors pre-selection section), we reduced 4 finite-dipole descriptors (i.e., FDH1, FDH2, FDV1, and FDV2) to 2, namely FDH_{mean} and FDV_{mean} , with the former being the averaged descriptor related to the horizontally oriented dipoles (FDH1 and FDH2) and the latter being the averaged descriptor related to the vertically oriented dipoles (FDV1 and FDV2).

To improve and facilitate the use of such a procedure, we developed a GUI with an algorithm enabling geometric transformations (i.e., translation and rotation) of both dipole and NM moieties.

2.3 GUI for NMs' surface descriptors

To ensure reproducibility in the calculation of the interaction energy between finite dipoles and NMs (essential to deriving the FDV and FDH descriptors), we devised an algorithm that automates the placement of dipoles above specific NM surfaces. This algorithm not only streamlines the process but also ensures consistent dipole positioning across the NM surface, adhering to the criteria defined in the Nanomaterials - quantum-mechanical

126 & surface descriptors section. By leveraging computationally efficient symmetry operations and linear trans-
127 formations based on quaternion algebra, the algorithm significantly reduces the time required for 3D rotations
128 and translations.

129 Building upon this algorithm, we developed a user-friendly graphical interface (GUI) to further enhance
130 efficiency. This Python 3-based application, utilizing libraries like NumPy [41] and Pandas [42], can load
131 multiple NM structures (including dipole in *.xyz format), enabling the rapid and standardized creation of
132 NM-dipole structures in four distinct configurations. Moreover, the application facilitates the calculation of
133 selected descriptors from the first and second groups (mentioned earlier) with respect to surface area and
134 generates Gaussian16 [43] input files, thereby streamlining the entire descriptor generation process. Details are
135 available in the attached manual and the desktop application can be downloaded from GitHub.

136 2.4 Molecular modeling

137 Well-tempered metadynamics (AWT-MetaD) simulations, implemented within the GROMACS molecular dy-
138 namics package, were employed to quantify the adsorption forces between biomolecules and nanomaterials. This
139 involved calculating the potential of mean force (PMF) representing the interactions between NMs and AAs.

140 Each simulation system comprised a biomolecular fragment positioned 1.5 nm above a silver slab, solvated
141 with TIP3P water, and neutralized with 0.15 M KCl. The resulting simulation boxes, with dimensions approx-
142 imately 2.4 nm × 2.4 nm × 8.5 nm, were initially equilibrated under NPT and NVT ensemble conditions for
143 30 ns each, ensuring proper system density and dimensions. A constant temperature of 300 K and pressure
144 of 1 bar were maintained throughout. The Nose-Hoover thermostat (5 ps relaxation time) was used for NVT
145 simulations, while a Berendsen weak-coupling thermostat and barostat were used for NPT. Periodic boundary
146 conditions were applied in all cases.

147 Following equilibration, AWT-MetaD simulations were conducted for at least 600 ns under NVT conditions
148 to ensure sufficient sampling and generate accurate PMF profiles. The PLUMED plugin was used to implement
149 AWT-MetaD within GROMACS. The collective variable (CV) defining the one-dimensional adsorption PMF
150 was the surface-to-surface distance (SSD), sampled from 0.0 to 2.0 nm, as defined in Ref. 34. A bias factor of
151 20 and a Gaussian hill height of 2.5 kJ/mol (added every 0.5 ps) were utilized, with a constant temperature of
152 300 K.

153 Convergence of the AWT-MetaD simulations was assessed by monitoring the evolution of three key param-
154 eters: (1) the SSD CV, (2) the height of the added Gaussian hills, and (3) the free energy difference between
155 the PMF minimum and the global minimum energy state.

156 In all cases, molecular modelling produces a tabulated potential, $U(r)$ describing the interaction between
157 the biomolecule and the surface of interest. This potential provides a substantial amount of information, and,
158 while it can be predicted by ML methods, for the purposes of this study we are interested in a more concise
159 descriptor. Thus, we extract adsorption energy from the PMF by numerically evaluating the integral,

$$E_{ads} = -k_B T \ln \left[\frac{\int_0^\delta e^{-U(r)/k_B T} dr}{\int_0^\delta dr} \right] \quad (1)$$

160 where δ is the distance at which we assume the molecule is unbound and is taken to be 1.0 nm. This provides
161 a single value for each NP-biomolecule pair for use in the ML modelling.

162 3 Implementation

163 3.1 Dataset for QSPR modeling

164 The dataset used for QSPR modeling consisted of 300 pairs being a unique combination of 20 NMs and 15
165 AAs, along with their corresponding adsorption energies obtained from molecular dynamics simulations (Sup-
166 plementMaterialData.xlsx, sheet: ModelingData). The NM-AA pairs were sorted by adsorption energy and
167 then divided into training and validation sets using a 2:1 split, resulting in 200 pairs in the training set and
168 100 pairs in the validation set. To ensure a balanced distribution of adsorption energy values and prevent
169 extrapolation errors, the pairs NM-AA with extreme values of adsorption energy were included in the training
170 set. The training set was used for model calibration, while the validation set was only used for the first stage
171 of external validation to verify the prediction ability and did not affect the form of QSPR model in any way.

172 Additionally, an extra validation set (EVS) comprising new 325 NM-biomolecule pairs was established to
173 improve predictability, as the second stage of external validation. This set encompasses 27 NMs, including 7
174 new nanomaterials, and 15 distinct biomolecules (Figure 1). Figure 3 provides a schematic presentation of the
175 NM-AA/biomolecule pairs used for the calibration and validation of the QSPR model.

176 3.2 Descriptors pre-selection

177 The feature selection process was employed to identify the most informative descriptors for characterizing the
178 adsorption energy interactions between biomolecules and NMs. Starting with an initial pool of 116 and 22
179 descriptors for AAs and NMs respectively, we first eliminated descriptors with low variance, using a threshold
180 of $Var[X] > p(1 - p)$ with $p = 0.8$. This initial step aimed to reduce noise and redundancy in the descriptors
181 set.

182 A univariate feature selection test was then performed, utilizing Pearson’s correlation coefficient for linear
183 dependencies and mutual information for non-linear relationships. This process ensured that only the most
184 relevant descriptors were retained for further analysis.

185 Initially, 8 descriptors were selected for both AAs and NMs. For AAs, these included BLTD48, ECC, ESOL,
186 MW (Molecular Weight), O%, SATot (Total Surface Area), Si, and UNIP (Unipolarity). For NMs, the selected
187 descriptors comprised Dipole moment (Debye), FDH_{mean} (Mean of Finite Dipole Horizontal energy in kcal/mol),
188 FDV1 and FDV2 (Finite Dipole Vertical energy in kcal/mol for both charge configurations), HOMO and LUMO
189 eigenvalues (eV), Quadrupole moment (Debye $\times\text{\AA}$), and Σ Pauling electronegativity per square \AA^2 .
190 However, BLTD48 was subsequently removed due to its coincidental correlation with energy. Additionally, two
191 closely related dipole interaction descriptors were averaged to further refine the descriptor set.

192 Relying on backward elimination, the final set of selected descriptors included 4 key AA/biomolecule descrip-
193 tors (ECC, MW, SATot, UNIP) and 5 crucial NM descriptors (Dipole moment, FDH_{mean} , FDV_{mean} , Quadrupole
194 moment, Σ Pauling electronegativity/ \AA^2). These descriptors were deemed to be the most informative for charac-
195 terizing the adsorption energy interactions between AAs and NMs, providing a foundation for the development
196 of robust predictive models.

197 3.3 QSPR modeling

198 To construct the QSPR of NM-AA/biomolecule interactions, we employed the AdaBoost regression approach.
199 This boosting algorithm, applicable to both classification and regression tasks, typically uses one-level decision
200 trees (stumps) as base learners [44, 45, 46, 47]. In each iteration, AdaBoost trains and evaluates the error of
201 all available stumps, progressively increasing the weight of misclassified observations. This iterative process
202 culminates in a robust ensemble classifier built from the combination of multiple weak learners.

203 Our AdaBoost Regressor model was constructed using 27 Decision Tree Regressor estimators, each with a
204 maximum depth of 3, and a linear loss function. To ensure reproducibility, the random_state parameter was
205 set to 975. The model was calibrated using the training dataset and validated on an independent validation
206 dataset. Model performance was assessed by computing the determination coefficient (R^2_{training}) and the root-
207 mean-square error ($RMSE_{\text{training}}$) for the training dataset predictions.

208 To verify the model robustness and generalization, we performed 5-fold internal cross-validation using the
209 ShuffleSplit algorithm, with a random_state of 8669 to ensure reproducibility. Within each fold, 25% of the
210 data was used as a test subset and various performance metrics ($R^2_{\text{cv-training}}$, $RMSE_{\text{cv-training}}$, $R^2_{\text{cv-validation}}$,
211 $RMSE_{\text{cv-validation}}$) were calculated.

212 The model predictive capability was assessed through external validation on the independent regular and
213 extra validation sets containing 100 NM-AA pairs and 325 NM-biomolecule pairs, respectively. Predictions were
214 generated for both sets, and R^2 and RMSE were calculated.

215 To visualize the model’s applicability domain and limitations, a Williams plot [48] was constructed using
216 the training set. The plot displays standard deviations on the y -axis (calculated from the PMF values in the
217 training set and corresponding predictions) and NM-AA/biomolecule pairs distribution in descriptor space on
218 the x -axis. The plot’s boundaries are defined by the leverage (h_k) parameter on the x -axis and a 3σ distance
219 on the y -axis, with h_k indicating structural similarity between objects.

220 4 Results

221 In this study, we applied meta-modeling approach combining physics-based methods and machine learning algo-
222 rithms to identify and quantify factors responsible for biomolecule adsorption on nanomaterials surfaces in the
223 bio-corona formation process. We simulated adsorption energy extracted from potentials of mean force (PMF)
224 calculated using the metadynamics method and linked with the structures of biomolecules and nanomaterials.
225 An important preliminary step was the development of a set of novel descriptors characterizing the surface
226 properties of nanomaterials. As a result, we developed the QSPR model, which could be applied to predict the
227 strength of nano-bio interaction between biomolecules and newly developed nanomaterials.

228 We calibrated the model using the training set of 200 NM-AA pairs (Figure 3), enabling the identification
229 and quantification of key factors influencing biomolecules adsorption in these systems (Figure 4). The feature
230 importance plot elucidated the relative significance of nanomaterials and biomolecules (precisely, AA used in
231 the training set) descriptors within the model. The newly developed NMs surface property descriptor FDV_{mean}

Figure 3: Schematic presentation of the NM-AA/biomolecules pairs distribution across the training (grey points), validation (navy blue points), and extra validation sets (where green points are in the model domain, purple points are extrapolated).

Figure 4: Feature importance plot for the AdaBoost regression model, indicating the relative importance of each descriptor in predicting the nano-bio interaction energy.

Figure 5: Predicted vs. observed adsorption energy for the training/validation set (left) and the EVS and EVS-WO (right).

232 and molecular weight (MW) of biomolecules emerged as the most pivotal descriptors, shedding light on the
 233 electrostatic and exchange interactions governing biomolecule adsorption onto NM surfaces. This is consistent
 234 with previous studies that have highlighted the importance of electrostatic interactions in protein adsorption [9].
 235 The research also revealed moderately significant descriptors like quadrupole moment of NMs, total surface
 236 area of biomolecules (SA_{tot}), and NMs' dipole moment, which contribute meaningfully to the model's overall
 237 performance. Less significant descriptors like eccentricity of biomolecules (ECC), NMs' FDH_{mean}, unipolarity
 238 of biomolecules (UNIP), and NMs' ΣPauling electronegativity were also identified, suggesting that these factors
 239 may play a less prominent role in the adsorption process for the studied systems.

240 The developed QSPR model, incorporating 9 descriptors selected on the basis of the feature importance
 241 analysis, demonstrated satisfactory statistical significance, as evidenced by R² and RMSE values across the
 242 training set (Table 3, Figure 5). To confirm the predictive capacities of the QSPR model, two external validation
 243 sets were used: i) a regular validation set of 100 NM-AA pairs, and ii) an extra validation set (EVS) of 325 NM
 244 pairs with more structurally diversified biomolecules. Statistical parameters calculated for the regular validation
 245 set are coherent with results for the training set (NM-AA). However, results for EVS are subject to greater
 246 error due to the presence of outliers in the set (Figure 6).

247 The analysis of R² and RMSE characteristics yielded satisfactory results, indicating the model's capabil-
 248 ity for accurate predictions when outliers are excluded (see EVS-WO, SupplementMaterialData.xlsx, sheet:
 249 EVS-WithoutOutliers). The William's plot analysis further revealed the applicability domain of the model,
 250 highlighting that a substantial proportion of objects from the training and validation datasets fall within this
 251 domain, affirming their compatibility with the model's predictive capabilities (Figure 6). However, certain ob-
 252 jects, including GLU-Au100 from the training set and ASN-Au100 and PHE-Au100 from the validation set,
 253 were identified as outliers outside the applicability domain. This suggests that the model may not be suitable
 254 for predicting adsorption energies for all possible combinations of NMs and biomolecules, and that further

Table 3: Statistical parameters of the AdaBoost model for the training and validation sets, including results from 5-fold CV, EVS and EVS-WO.

Set	R^2	RMSE	R^2_{cv}	RMSE _{cv}
Training	0.84	1.52	0.83	1.34
Validation	0.70	1.94	0.72	1.88
EVS	0.46	2.41	-	-
EVS-WO	0.69	1.47	-	-

Figure 6: Williams plot showing the applicability domain of the model for the training/validation set (left) and the EVS and EVS-WO (right). The plot displays standardized residuals versus leverages for each NM-AA/biomolecule pair. The warning leverage ($h_k=0.15$) and standardized residual thresholds ($\pm 3\sigma$) are indicated by dashed lines. Objects outside these lines are considered outliers.

refinement may be necessary to improve its generalizability, potentially by incorporating protein flexibility as demonstrated by Rouse et al. [20]

The model’s robustness is evident in its accurate predictions for the majority of NM-AA combinations within the training and regular validation datasets (R^2_{cv} and $RMSE_{cv}$). This is consistent with previous findings that machine learning approaches, particularly those employing quantum-mechanical descriptors can effectively predict adsorption energies [49]. However, the model’s performance was less reliable for specific scenarios involving gold (Au100) nanoparticles in combination with certain amino acids (GLU, ASN, PHE), as well as for some objects based on silver (Ag) nanoparticles and functionalized carbon nanotubes within the external validation set (Figure 5, 6, Table 4). These discrepancies highlight potential limitations in the model’s generalizability and underscore the need for further refinement, potentially through the incorporation of additional descriptors, extending the training set or the exploration of alternative ML algorithms.

The identified groups of NM-biomolecule pairs with Au100, G1, and G2, along with individual pairs with Au100, Ag111, and Ag100, provides further insights into the model’s performance (Table 4). The Au100 group, despite exhibiting structural similarity, showed limited predictive capabilities, with predictions falling below the desired threshold. The G1 group, while sharing structural similarity, also exhibited relatively weak predictions. The G2 group, comprising NMs lacking structural similarity, also showed suboptimal predictions. These findings emphasize the need for further investigation into the factors influencing the model’s performance for specific NM-biomolecule combinations, as suggested by Docter et al. [50]. The variability observed in these groups could be attributed to factors such as surface curvature and packing efficiency, as demonstrated in the hard-sphere model by Rouse and Lobaskin [19]. Saptarshi et al. (2013) [49] also emphasize that the bioreactivity of NMs is a complex phenomenon influenced by multiple factors, which may explain the observed discrepancies in the model’s predictions for certain NM-biomolecule combinations. Further research incorporating additional descriptors or alternative ML algorithms could enhance the model’s overall predictive capability, particularly for materials exhibiting atypical adsorption behaviors.

Table 4: Objects (NM-AA or NM-biomolecule interactions) identified as outliers in the Williams plot (see Figure 6 analysis), along with their leverage h^* and σ values.

Name	h^*	σ	Name	h^*	σ
CNT-NH3(+)-low···DMEP (G2)	0.18	-8.35	Au100···THR	0.03	3.92
CNT-NH3(+)-high···DMEP (G2)	0.18	-6.50	Au100···HID	0.05	3.92
Ag100···DMEP (G2)	0.21	-5.82	Au100···ASPP	0.03	3.96
Ag100···BGLCNA	0.64	-5.29	Au100···VAL	0.03	4.13
C-amorph···BGLC (G1)	0.12	-4.92	Au100···BGLCNA	0.62	4.19
CNT-COO(-)-low···BGLC (G1)	0.11	-4.64	Au100···MAMM	0.03	4.22
Ag111···BGLC (G1)	0.10	-4.41	Ag100···AFUC	0.09	4.37
CNT-COO(-)-high···BGLC (G2)	0.31	-4.27	Au100···NC4	0.11	4.96
CNT-NH3(+)-low···CYM (G1)	0.02	-4.10	Au100···MAS	0.03	5.32
Ag110···CYM (G1)	0.03	-3.65	Au100···GLUP	0.03	5.68
CNT-NH3(+)-high···CYM (G1)	0.03	-3.52	Au100···HIP	0.06	5.91
Ag111···BGLCNA (G1)	0.63	-3.38	Au100···BGLC	0.10	6.37

Importantly, the observation that most prediction errors on the biomolecule side originated from the external validation set suggests that the model’s performance might be influenced by the specific characteristics of the biomolecules included and/or omitted in the training data. This observation underscores the importance of utilizing diverse and representative datasets in developing predictive models for complex biological phenomena. The results align with observations from other studies, where the accuracy of protein adsorption energy predictions was found to be sensitive to the choice of protein structure, particularly for smaller nanoparticles [20]. The variability in binding energies due to structural perturbations, especially for smaller nanoparticles, emphasizes the need for careful consideration of protein structure in adsorption modeling.

The observed discrepancies in the model’s predictions for certain NM-biomolecule combinations may be attributed to several factors. The complexity of the nano-bio interface suggests the selected descriptors may not fully capture the forces involved in adsorption for all NMs and biomolecules [2, 51]. Model performance may also be influenced by the specific biomolecules in the training data, as most prediction errors on the biomolecule side originated from the external validation set. This aligns with studies emphasizing the importance of nanoparticle size and surface chemistry in protein corona composition [3]. Binding energy variability due to structural perturbations, especially for smaller nanoparticles, further underscores the need for careful consideration of both NM and biomolecule properties in adsorption modeling [10]. Additionally, the assumption of protein rigidity in the United Atom model used in the metadynamics simulations, while computationally efficient, may not fully account for conformational changes upon adsorption, as mentioned by Rouse et al. [20].

297 Compared to traditional experimental methods, MM simulation methods provide a detailed understanding of
298 atomic-level interactions, which is crucial for designing safe and effective nanomaterials. However, MM remains
299 computationally demanding, especially for complex systems and long simulations. Integrating ML techniques
300 with MM offers a promising solution. This synergy opens the door to developing predictive models capable
301 of capturing the complex relationships between the structures of nanomaterials and biomolecules and their
302 adsorption energies. ML model, trained on carefully selected data from MM simulations, can predict these
303 energies much faster and with less computational effort than further MM simulations. This approach not only
304 speeds up research but also allows for the efficient screening of a huge number of potential nanomaterials, which
305 is particularly important in the context of SSbD. It should be emphasized that combining MM with ML is not
306 intended to replace MM simulation, but rather to optimize them. MM provides the high-quality data necessary
307 for learning ML models, which in turn enables efficient exploration of the parameter space and prediction of
308 the properties of new NMs.

309 5 Conclusion

310 Bio-corona formation around nanoparticles in the biological environment is a critical factor influencing their
311 behavior and fate within the organisms, thus necessitating comprehensive investigation within the field of NM
312 research. Our study demonstrates the successful application of a meta-modeling approach integrating high-level
313 theory, and molecular modeling with an efficient data-driven machine-learning algorithm for the investigation
314 of nano-bio interaction. The developed quantitative structure-property relationship model is built on simplified
315 descriptors for both biomolecules and nanoparticles and offers a streamlined alternative to computationally
316 intensive molecular dynamics simulations, as exemplified by the work of Power et al., while maintaining com-
317 mendable predictive accuracy. The data, algorithms and GUI for NMs' surface descriptors are made available
318 in accordance with the FAIR principle (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable). However, while our model
319 demonstrates promising predictive capabilities, the identified limitations underscore the need for ongoing re-
320 search to enhance the accuracy and generalizability of such models, paving the way for a deeper understanding of
321 the protein corona phenomenon and its implications for NM design and applications, particularly in biomedicine.

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